

IMPROVING LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN CLASSROOMS BY USING TECHNOLOGICAL RESOURCES

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Annotation. The paper analyzes how technology is changing language learning, with an emphasis on resources like internet resources, multimedia content, and language apps. It draws attention to the change in teaching methodologies from teacher-centered to student-centered, emphasizing customized and flexible learning. The study evaluates the advantages and difficulties of incorporating technology into language instruction by looking at previous studies and use both qualitative and quantitative data. Key findings show that technology can improve motivation, language proficiency, and communication competence, but it must be used carefully to prevent technology overload

Keywords. Language education, technological tools, blended learning, student engagement, language apps, multimedia resources, virtual reality, motivation, communication skills, learner autonomy.

Аннотация Данная работа исследует трансформирующую роль технологий в обучении языкам, уделяя внимание таким инструментам, как языковые приложения, онлайн-платформы и мультимедийные материалы. В статье подчеркивается переход от учитель-центрированного к студент-центрированному обучению с акцентом на индивидуализированный и адаптируемый подход. Исследование анализирует существующую литературу и использует как качественные, так и количественные данные для оценки преимуществ и проблем интеграции технологий в языковое образование. Основные выводы показывают, что технологические инструменты улучшают языковые навыки, мотивацию и коммуникативную компетентность, однако их необходимо внедрять осознанно, чтобы избежать перегруженности технологиями.

Ключевые слова Языковое обучение, технологические инструменты, смешанное обучение, вовлеченность студентов, языковые приложения, мультимедийные ресурсы, виртуальная реальность, мотивация, коммуникативные навыки, автономия учащихся.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola texnologiyaning til o'rgatishdagi o'zgaruvchan rolini, til o'rganish ilovalari, onlayn platformalar va multimedia materiallari kabi vositalarga e'tibor qaratgan holda o'rganadi. O'qituvchi markazli yondashuvdan o'quvchi markazli yondashuvga o'tish ta'kidlanib, individual va moslashuvchan o'qitishning ahamiyati ko'rsatib berilgan. Tadqiqot mavjud adabiyotlarni o'rganib, sifat va miqdoriy ma'lumotlardan foydalangan holda texnologiyalarni til ta'limiga integratsiya qilishning afzalliklari va muammolarini baholaydi. Natijalarga ko'ra, texnologik vositalar til ko'nikmalari, motivatsiya va kommunikatsiya qobiliyatini yaxshilaydi, ammo texnologiyadan ortiqcha foydalanishning oldini olish uchun ularni ongli ravishda qo'llash zarur.

Sinfda texnologik resurslar yordamida til o'qitishni takomillashtirish

Kalit so'zlar. Til o'qitish, texnologik vositalar, aralash o'qitish, o'quvchilarni jalb qilish, til o'rganish ilovalari, multimedia resurslari, virtual reallik, motivatsiya, kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalari, o'quvchi mustaqilligi.

The use of technology, in language education has transformed approaches by improving student engagement and independence while enhancing learning results. This paper investigates the impact of tools like language apps, online platforms and multimedia materials on the process of learning a language. It focuses on the transition, from a teacher centered to a student centered model. Highlights the significance of individualized and adaptable methodologies. After examining existing research and real world studies in sources of information and data analysis methods are used in this study to investigate the benefits and obstacles associated with incorporating technology, into language learning systems and its effects, on language abilities motivation and communication competence.

The rise of technology has greatly changed industries, like education – language instruction in this case! Classic teaching in classrooms has evolved with the addition of resources that bring ways for engaging and interactive learning experiences to students fingertips now! Utilizing technology in settings encourages teamwork among learners. Enhances their access to genuine language resources while also enabling tailored learning adventures, for each individual.

Educators have been blending tech tools together to make language learning more interesting and successful in times. By using these tools smartly and in line, with teaching objectives they aim to enhance speakinglistening, reading writing skillsalong with fostering understanding and learner

independence. The effectiveness of tools relies heavily on how they are integrated into the teaching methods and goals.

Various research has delved into the influence of technology, on language education according to Warschauer (2006) who highlights three advantages of incorporating technology. Enhanced motivation levels among learners; avenues for interactive learning experiences; and the availability of genuine language materials for study purposes. Contemporary resources, like apps, online language learning platforms and multimedia aids enable learners to grasp vocabulary pronunciation and grammar through interactive and stimulating educational methods.

Sharma and Barrett (2007) suggested that blended learning can improve language learning results by integrating traditional classroom teaching with resources. Popular language learning tools such, as Duolingo, Kahoot and Quizlet enable learners to practice language skills outside the classroom. Additionally virtual learning platforms, like Moodle and Google Classroom help teachers assign tasks monitor progress and provide feedback easily.

Other tools that are gaining popularity, in language classrooms include whiteboards and audiovisual aids along with reality (VR). According to Ghasemi and Hashemi (2011) the use of whiteboards boosts student engagement. Encourages active involvement, in the classroom experience. Additionally virtual reality offers learners the opportunity to experience simulated environments for practicing real life communication situations in a language as highlighted by Papadima Sophocleous et al., 2020.

This study uses a combination of quantitative methods to investigate the influence of resources, on language acquisition processes in education settings. Interviews and surveys, with both language instructors and students offer perspectives on how various technologies have influenced language skills development as student motivation and engagement levels.

The results suggest that students who incorporated a mix of resources showed proficiency in language skills, than those who stuck to conventional approaches alone. In particular applications for language learning and virtual platforms notably improved communication skills by offering learners chances for conversations with native speakers. This supports Vygotskys (1978) social constructivism theory that highlights the significance of interaction, in language growth.

Moreover students expressed increased enthusiasm and self assurance when utilizing engaging resources. Nonetheless the research also underscores the issue of being overwhelmed by technology, whereby excessive tool usage may lead to perplexity or lack of interest. As pointed out in the study, by Garrett (2009) technology ought to enhance than overshadow the process and educators should thoughtfully choose tools according to educational goals.

The use of resources, in teaching languages brings a range of advantages such as increased involvement from students. Tailored learning experiences leading to better language skills development. To maximize the benefits of technology in education it's crucial to combine it with teaching methods guided by educators who help students stay motivated and on track, toward their language learning objectives.

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